

2. Urea hydrolyzed in oxidized and reduced flooded Sumatra soil at 25 °C. Louisiana State University, Baton Rouge, USA, 1988.

The results show that rate of urea hydrolysis in the oxidized soil proceeded at a significantly slower rate than in the reduced soil for all the incubation periods (Fig. 2). At 1 d after application, 40% of added urea was hydrolyzed in the oxidized soil, and 62% in the reduced soil. At 4 d, 72% of added urea was hydrolyzed in the oxidized soil, and 93% in the reduced soil. At 7 d, a small amount of urea still remained in the oxidized soil, but no trace was found in the reduced soil. □

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Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Influence of P, K, micronutrients, and dolomite on azolla growth

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We studied the effects of P, K, micronutrients (M), and dolomite (D) on azolla growth and its P accumulation in 1.2- × 2.3-m plots in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. The test was conducted at 1,260 m altitude at the end of the warm season Mar 1985 (air temperature 16-25 °C; water temperature 11-40 °C) in Antananarivo.

Soil was sandy clay loam mineral hydromorph, with pH 5.2, 1.13% total P, 0.155% Olsen P, 3% organic matter, 1.7% C, and ex-K 0.18 meq/100 g.

Treatments were P alone; P and K; P, K, and M; P, K, and D; and P, K, M,

and D. P was applied at 7 kg/ha as triple superphosphate, K at 5 kg/ha as KCl, and M at 10 kg/ha as a commercial cocktail containing 0.3% B, 1.5% Fe, 0.5% Cu, 1.5% Mn, 0.01% Mo, 1.5% Zn, 4% MgO, 5% N, and 5% S. Dolomite was applied at 300 kg/ha. P was applied weekly at 7 kg/ha; the other materials were applied only at the beginning of the test. Dolomite was applied to estimate the influence of pH changes.

Azolla growth and P accumulation during 37 d at the end of the warm season in 1985, Antananarivo, Madagascar.

Treatment	Azolla wt		P accumulated	
	g	Increase over control (%)	%	Increase over control (%)
Control	110	—	0.059	—
P	270	157	0.197	235
P+K	280	169	0.200	239
P+K+M	340	218	0.198	236
P+K+D	310	189	0.205	247
P+K+M+D	350	228	0.211	258
LSD (0.05)	101		0.102	

Azolla pinnata var. *pinnata* (var. *africana*) was inoculated at 50 g/plot. Azolla fresh weight and P accumulation were recorded 37 d after inoculation.

Results show that P is essential to azolla growth (see table). Fronds cultivated with P were reddish green. P-deficient fronds were reddish brown, and their roots were long and easily detached. Dolomite, micronutrients, P, and K together induced uniform azolla multiplication. K did not influence frond proliferation.

P accumulation was remarkable. Azolla incorporated as green manure could be a source of available P. □

Response of flooded rice to green manure

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We studied the relative contribution of N from aboveground (shoot) and